

Dissemination/Communication Report

Project title: “Environmental effects on physical properties of smart composites and FRP modified by carbonaceous nanofillers for structural applications”.

Project No. 1.1.1.2/VIAA/1/16/066.

Period concerning this report: 01.01.2020-31.12.2020.

**Activity 1.1.1.2 “Post-doctoral Research Aid” of the Specific Aid
Objective 1.1.1 “To increase the research and innovative capacity of
scientific institutions of Latvia and the ability to attract external
financing, investing in human resources and infrastructure” of the
Operational Programme “Growth and Employment”.**

Summary

During the third year of the project implementation different dissemination/communication activities were carried out.

The scientific results of the project were published in one scientific paper in *Polymers* (Q1 open access journal, IF 3.2). The scientific paper about seasonal hydrothermal environmental effects on some physical properties of the epoxy and epoxy-based nanocomposites and basalt fibre-reinforced plastics (BFRP) was submitted to *Polymer Degradation and Stability* (Q1 journal, IF 4.03) by the end of 2020. For the dissemination of information among general public professional *FACEBOOK* profile was regularly updated with press releases regarding the project activities. The project profile “Environmental effects on physical properties of smart composites and fibre-reinforced plastics modified by carbonaceous nanofillers for structural applications” was updated with annual reports at open-access database *ZENODO* (www.zenodo.org) under community POSTDOC-Latvia providing open-access to all published materials.

1. Objectives

- Dissemination of results;
- Communication;
- Knowledge and data management and protection.

2. Work planned for this reporting period

T4.1. Dissemination of results

- Preparation and publishing of one popular scientific publication and quarter press releases in the website of the University of Latvia (LU, www.lu.lv);
- Self-activation of all project-related publications within LU repository (www.dspace.lu.lv) and subject-based repository (*ResearchGate*).

T4.2. Communication

- Implementation of the communication plan;
- Attendance of international conferences (e.g. *ICSAAM 2020*, Patras, Greece).

T4.3. Knowledge and data management and protection

- Transfer of generated data to the central database (e.g. *Dropbox*), and its preservation for at least five years after completion of the project.

3. Progress

T4.1. Dissemination of results

During the third year of project implementation, 4 quarter press releases (#9-12) were prepared and published on the website of LU (<https://www.lu.lv/zinatne/programmas-un-projekti/es-strukturfondi/1112pasakums-pecdoktoranturas-petniecibas-atbalsts-1karta/vides-ietekme-uz-viedo-ar-oglekla-nanopildvielam-modificetu-kompozitu-un-skiedru-plastikatu-fizikalajam-ipasibam-strukturaliem-pielietojumiem/>).

Based on the project results one scientific paper on hydrothermal ageing of an epoxy resin filled with carbon nanofillers was published in Q1 scientific journal having open

access (*Polymers*). One scientific paper on seasonal hydrothermal environmental effects on some physical properties of the epoxy and epoxy-based nanocomposites and basalt fibre-reinforced plastics (BFRP) was submitted to *Polymer Degradation and Stability* (Q1 journal, IF 4.03) by the end of 2020.

For the dissemination of project results among general public one popular scientific publication “Smart materials in external environmental conditions” (in Latvian) was published in news portal of the University of Latvia, <https://www.lu.lv/par-mums/lu-mediji/zinas/zina/t/59232>.

For the same purpose, a professional *FACEBOOK* profile was updated with 5 press releases (<https://www.facebook.com/tatjana.glaskovakuzmina>) on the project activities during the third year of project implementation.

Four project applications were prepared and submitted for different scientific calls to assure sustainability and continuity of the project results (2 M-era.Net, 1 Baltic research programme, and 1 Nordic Energy Research) supervising the project or representing LU.

T4.2. Communication

According to dissemination/communication plan (D4.1, M12) developed during the first year of project implementation certain dissemination/communication activities were carried out.

Several presentations on the project and its current results were made for the progress seminars organized in the Institute for Mechanics of Materials of LU (Riga, Latvia).

A presentation on current project results was prepared and reported for the invited lecture at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Gjøvik, Norway) for PhD course “Advanced materials” on 10.12.2020.

T4.3. Knowledge and data management and protection

All data generated (raw and ready data files, reports, presentations) were transferred to the folder of POSTDOC project in the central database *Dropbox* providing access to scientific supervisor from UL Dr. Sc. Ing. Andrey Aniskevich and representative person of IPCB Dr. Sc. Ing. Mauro Zarrelli. All data files will be preserved in *Dropbox* during the project implementation and at least five years after completion of the project.

4. Significant results

Scientific publications (2020)

1. Glaskova-Kuzmina T., Aniskevich A., Zotti A., Borriello A. and Zarrelli M. “Flexural properties of the epoxy resin filled with single and hybrid carbon nanofillers”. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2020, 1431, 012001. DOI: 10.1088/1742-6596/1431/1/012001.
2. Glaskova-Kuzmina T., Aniskevich A., Sevchenko J., Borriello A., and Zarrelli M. Moisture sorption by epoxy resin filled with MWCNT of different thickness. *Proceedings of European Conference on Composite Materials 2018*, 2020, Athens, Greece, code 155810.
3. Glaskova-Kuzmina T., Aniskevich A., Papanicolaou G., Portan D., Zotti A., Borriello A., and Zarrelli M. Hydrothermal aging of an epoxy resin filled with carbon nanofillers. *Polymers*, 2020, Vol. 12, 1153; DOI:10.3390/polym12051153.

Popular scientific publications (2020)

1. Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina. Smart materials in external environmental conditions (in Latvian). News portal of the University of Latvia, 2020, <https://www.lu.lv/par-mums/lu-mediji/zinas/zina/t/59232>.

Submitted project proposals (2020)

1. “Sustainable and durable basalt fibre reinforced plastics for efficient urban transport“, Baltic Research Programme 2020, Project coordinator Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina (the proposal was submitted in October 2020 and is under consideration).
2. “Polymer composite construction reinforced with a customized 3D fabric“, M-Era.Net 2020, Project leader from LU Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina (full proposal has been submitted in November 2020 and is under consideration).
3. “Predictive Multiparametric Modelling for Optimal Repair of Composite Wind Turbine Blades“, Baltic-Nordic Energy Research Programme 2020. Project coordinator Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina (the proposal didn’t meet the criteria and was rejected).
4. “Smart High-Performance Composites for Energy & Transport“, M-Era.Net 2020, Project leader from LU Tatjana Glaskova-Kuzmina (the pre-proposal didn’t meet the criteria and was rejected).

Presentations at international conferences

No presentations were made in 2020 because of the cancellation of the planned conference (ICSAAM 2020, Patras, Greece) due to COVID-19. Therefore, the focus was made on the preparation of scientific papers and project applications instead of presenting the results at international conferences.

5. Deviations from the working plan

Positive deviations from the working plan of dissemination/communication were obtained. The total number of conference presentations and published scientific papers written in the project proposal (2 presentations and 2 scientific papers) is higher (6 presentations and 7 publications indexed in Scopus/WoS) maximizing the impact of the project.

6. Corrective actions

-Participation in online study courses “Theoretical and practical guide to the proposal writing of H2020/Horizon Europe projects” and “Financial management of H2020 projects theoretical and practical approach” organized by EFMC in 2020 to improve professional skills in writing and management of project proposals.

-Preparation and submission of 4 project proposals for different scientific calls to assure sustainability and continuity of the project results (2 M-Era.Net, 1 Baltic research programme, and 1 Nordic Energy Research).

7. Deliverables and Milestones

D4.1 Annual dissemination/communication report (M12, M24, **M36**).